

Improving the system of formation of socio-cultural competences of students of general education schools

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the improvement of the system for developing socio-cultural competencies among secondary school students. And also, the main approaches to the implementation of the competency-based approach in the conditions of modern education are revealed based on the ideas of scientific teachers and methodologists on the content of education; The structure of competence is considered through the characteristics of value, cognitive, behavioral components and their main content on the educational process at school.

Currently, society is going through a difficult stage of reassessment of social and moral standards of life. This process is complex, often accompanied by a deformation of value orientations, a serious distortion of sociocultural competencies, ideas about the prestige of education, professionalism, and culture. Each generation builds its own model of life activity - a sociocultural space, consisting of certain meanings of leading concepts, a system of symbols, a system of values, sociocultural competencies and norms. It is in this space that the identification of the individual as a social subject and professional occurs. We call the density and coverage of culturally significant meanings in the activities and relationships of people sociocultural space.

It is characterized by the saturation of any social object with sociocultural competence and semantic content in terms of its compliance with the culture of a given society. In the context of the rapidly gaining momentum of the process of global integration, new requirements are put forward for the individual, the main asset of which should be a common culture and universal human values, the ability and desire to independently improve in their activities and participate in the formation of sociocultural competence. However, current sociocultural processes are so dynamic that they statement, and even more detailed consideration, require the development of new views on the study of sociocultural competencies.

Competence and competency are relatively new concepts, and therefore necessitate specification and clarification. In recent years, a large number of works have appeared in the scientific literature containing various definitions of competence. The range of these definitions is so wide and sometimes contradictory that we can safely say that modern science

faces challenges related to the definition, identification and justification of competencies (basic, key, supra-subject, subject-specific and others) and their structure, development of approaches to their assessment as a result of education .

According to A.V. Khutorskoy, competence is a set of interrelated personality qualities (knowledge, abilities, skills, methods of activity), specified in relation to a certain range of objects and processes and necessary to act in a qualitatively productive manner in relation to them. The researcher has determined a list of key educational competencies based on the main goals of general education, the structural representation of social experience and the personal experience of the student, allowing him to master social experience, gain life skills and practical activities in society. The author identifies seven key educational competencies: value-semantic, general cultural, educational-cognitive, informational, communicative, social-labor, personal self-improvement competence [2].

According to V.A. Bolotova, V.V. Serikov's nature of competence is a consequence of the individual's self-development, his not so much technological as personal growth, a consequence of self-organization and generalization of activity and personal experience. Competence is a way of existence of knowledge, skills, education, promoting personal self-realization, finding a student's place in the world, as a result of which education appears as highly motivated and, in a true sense, personality-oriented, ensuring the demand for personal potential, recognition of the individual by others and awareness of his own importance [1].

In the conditions of the sociocultural space, all the above definitions place emphasis on an activity-based approach to competencies. However, let us turn to the analysis of the essence of the value approach. Thus, the French philosopher M. Dufresne, in what he called his "inventory description of natural categories," identified three classes of values: goods aimed at possession, the pleasant, the useful and the beautiful; goods addressed to knowledge are true; goods that are respectful, sacred, humane, just.

Values are found in society, since values are the social existence of an object, phenomenon, etc. Therefore, the process of revaluation of values occurs constantly, along with the development of society and the individual. The value approach allows us to highlight the inner side of the relationship between the individual and society, to see the personal aspect of the student's orientation towards values and sociocultural competence. In the definition of A.Yu. Polenova sociocultural competence is defined as the ability of an individual to act consciously and productively in a situation of uncertainty. Positively solve vital problems of society, subjectively comprehending the possibilities of response behavior options for everyone, entering into social interaction with it, accepting various forms of cultural self-expression and creativity of positively oriented social groups and individuals as they master social space [3].

In his research, M. S. Kagan noted that the cataclysms that occurred in the twentieth century showed that only the organization of joint actions of peoples can allow the survival of the human race. And it is for this reason that today new systems of values are beginning to crystallize, with a new hierarchy of their interactions and a new dominant. The highest place in this hierarchy should be occupied by existential values, which, in turn, determine meaning and life positions [3].

Based on the views of T.V. Borovikova, A.Yu. Polenova, M.S. Kagan let us formulate a definition of sociocultural competence. Sociocultural competence, in our opinion, is the integration of knowledge, abilities, skills that contribute to the self-realization of senior schoolchildren in determining the meaning and life positions that ensure the formation of the moral stability of the individual: to withstand life's trials in the conditions of their development of the

sociocultural space. Sociocultural competence is defined as the ability and readiness to implement knowledge, abilities, skills, practical experience in real conditions of professional activity. The focus of the learning process on the development of sociocultural competence of high school students, improvement of their self-educational activities, as well as the development of general culture should be considered today as a general education strategy (value-semantic, value-statutory, value-oriented competencies). Sociocultural competence acts as the goal and result of preparing a student for sociocultural interaction with society. Modern sociocultural conditions actualize the need to educate modern schoolchildren with sociocultural competencies and a system of value relations towards their homeland, its spiritual identity. Modern youth have changed their attitude towards such values as national culture, public recognition, honor, interesting work, a sense of national pride, social equality, hard work, a sense of duty, internationalism, collectivism, etc., inherent in the Soviet period. The system of sociocultural competence, like any other system, successfully develops and functions only under certain conditions.

Using these conditions, we consider ways and means of interaction between a set of measures in the educational process aimed at developing sociocultural competence. Having examined the modern sociocultural conditions in which the development of schoolchildren's competencies is carried out and, having identified the factors that determine this process, we came to a number of conclusions related to taking into account the identified circumstances in the development of schoolchildren's competencies:

the development of schoolchildren's competencies in the educational process is determined by the socio-cultural conditions and factors that have developed in society;

education of sociocultural competencies for older schoolchildren must correspond to the "spirit" of the new millennium, which is characterized by humanity's awareness of the need for unity and the development of a single value consciousness, which is due to the threats that have emerged for humanity in the new millennium.

In this regard, the priority should be: instilling in schoolchildren a value-based attitude towards humanity, man, the Fatherland, home, nature; nurturing the ability to cooperate and dialogue.

Scientists emphasize the instability of the modern social world, which has largely weakened the traditions of modern Uzbek patriotic education. However, it is precisely in patriotism that pride in one's ancestors, in the history of one's country, nation, and people is always expressed. It is he who expresses the national spirit, the readiness to overcome the obstacles that history places before the people and society.

Thus, the main task in the formation of sociocultural competence of high school students remains the formation of the moral stability of the individual: to withstand life's trials in the conditions of their development of the sociocultural space.

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